

Appendix F

Presentation

GIS PROCEDURE FOR PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF POTENTIAL HYDROPOWER SITES

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OBJECTIVE

A GIS based analysis of potential hydropower sites is useful for planning and prioritizing development projects for government entities, developers, and renewable energy companies. This is a fast procedure to quantify available potential. The preliminary identification, and ranking of these sites provide the justification for further in-depth studies.

SOFTWARES

QGIS

- R.Contour.Step
- R.Watershed
- R.Water.Outlet
- R.To.Vect
- R.Relief
- V.To.Rast.Attribute
- NNJOIN
- Landscape Ecology
- Zonal Statistic

EXCEL

- Visual Basic

GOOGLE EARTH

- Maps History

PROCEDURE

Data Gathering

Data Processing

Hydrologic Analysis

Hydraulic Analysis

Exhibits

DATA GATHERING

QUAD MAP

AERIAL MAP

LIDAR

DEM

RAINFALL

FLOW DATA

LAND COVER

SOIL MAP

EVAPORATION

RIVERS

WATERFALLS

FAULT LINES

DATA PROCESSING

DEM

DEM RASTER FORMAT

R.Contour.Step

DEM VECTOR FORMAT

DATA PROCESSING

RAINFALL DEPTH (P)

(P) RASTER FORMAT

R.Contour.Step

(P) VECTOR FORMAT

THIS PROCESS IS REPEATED FOR ALL THE MONTHS

DATA PROCESSING

EVAPORATION (PET)

(PET) RASTER FORMAT

R.Contour.Step

(PET) VECTOR FORMAT

THIS PROCESS IS REPEATED FOR ALL THE MONTHS

DATA PROCESSING

SOILS TYPE

SOILS RASTER FORMAT

R.To.Vect

SOILS VECTOR FORMAT

ATTRIBUTES ARE MANIPULATED TO ADD HYDROLOGIC SOIL GROUP A, B, C, D, AND SOILS STORAGE CAPACITY BASED ON CLASSIFICATION

DATA PROCESSING

LAND COVER

COVER RASTER FORMAT

COVER VECTOR FORMAT

ATTRIBUTES ARE MANIPULATED TO ADD SCS-CN (CURVE NUMBER), BASED ON LAND COVER TYPE

DATA PROCESSING

SCS-CN

VECTOR FORMAT

NNJOIN

V.To.Rast.Attribute

SCS-CN VECTOR, RASTER FORMAT

ATTRIBUTES ARE MANIPULATED TO UPDATE SCS-CN (CURVE NUMBER),
BASED ON LAND COVER TYPE, AND HYDROLOGIC SOIL GROUPS

DATA PROCESSING

WATERSHEDS LIMITS

DEM RASTER FORMAT

R.Watershed

RASTER FORMAT

DATA PROCESSING

SITE BASIN

STREAM SEGMENT RASTER FORMAT

VECTOR FORMAT

A POINT ALONG THE STREAM SEGMENT IS SELECTED AS THE LOCATION OF THE DIVERSION STRUCTURE, AND THE SITE BASIN POLYGON IS CREATED

DATA PROCESSING

SITE BASIN - DATA

POPULATE DATA FROM P, PET, SOIL, SCS-CN TO SITE ATTRIBUTE

Landscape Ecology
or
Zonal
Statistic

Dec_PET_M	Soil_Capac	SCS_Mean	SCS_Min	SCS_Max
105.86	282	67.40	58.00	80.00
108.81	266	66.15	58.00	80.00
102.69	321	69.43	66.00	80.00
104.23	221	64.00	58.00	85.00
100.93	232	63.25	58.00	78.00
84.81	274	68.73	58.00	80.00
99.71	284	70.42	58.00	85.00
122.62	224	75.28	69.00	78.00
122.38	226	76.88	69.00	78.00
119.14	232	77.48	69.00	78.00

PARTIAL SNAPSHOT

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

WATER BALANCE

$$P = AET + RUNOFF + DFLOW + GWLOSS + BFLOW1 + \Delta S$$

DEFINITION:

P	Precipitation
PET	Potential Evapotranspiration
AET	Actual Evapotranspiration
RUNOFF	Surface Runoff (SCS)
DFLOW	Direct Flow to Stream
BFLOW1	Base Flow from Within Watershed
GWLOSS	Flow Loss to Groundwater
BFLOW2	Base Flow from Outside Watershed
ΔS	Change in Groundwater Storage

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

CALIBRATION VARIABLES

RFLK PSUB GWF GWL

DEFINITION:

RFLK	Fraction of Surface Runoff Flowing to the Stream
PSUB	Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Groundwater Layer
GWF	Fraction of Groundwater Flowing to the Stream
GWL	Fraction of Groundwater Flowing out of the Watershed

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

RUNOFF

Excess Runoff

$$RUNOFF = RFLK * \frac{(P - 0.2S)^2}{(P + 0.8S)}$$

Soil Storage

$$S = \frac{25400}{CN} - 254CN$$

SCS Curve Number CN

Dry Condition when $(P/PET) < 0.8$ – Antecedent Moisture Condition (I)

$$CN(I) = \frac{4.2CN(II)}{10 - 0.058CN(II)}$$

Normal Condition when $0.8 \leq (P/PET) < 0.9$ – Antecedent Moisture Condition (II)

$$CN(II) = CN$$

Wet Condition when $(P/PET) \geq 0.9$ – Antecedent Moisture Condition (III)

$$CN(III) = \frac{23CN(II)}{10 + 0.13CN(II)}$$

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

AET

Actual Evapotranspiration

Soil Storage Ratio

$$STORAT = \frac{STORAGE}{NOMINAL}$$

Where:

STORAGE is the available soil water storage at given time

NOMINAL is the soil storage capacity for the type of soil

Precipitation Ratio

$$PRERAT = \frac{P}{PET}$$

Actual Evapotranspiration

$$AET = \left[\left(\frac{STORAT}{2} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{STORAT}{2} \right) * PRERAT \right] * PET$$

Where:

P is the monthly precipitation depth

PET is the monthly potential evapotranspiration depth

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

EXMRAT

Excess Soil Moist Ratio

Water Balance

$$WATBAL = P - AET$$

Where:

P is the monthly precipitation depth

AET is the monthly actual evapotranspiration depth

For $WATBAL < 0$

$$EXMRAT = 0$$

Case when $STORAT > 1$

$$EXMRAT = 1 - (0.5 * (2 - STORAT)^2)$$

Case when $STORAT \leq 1$

$$EXMRAT = 0.5 * (STORAT)^2$$

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

EXMST, GWRECH, DELSTO

Excess Soil Moist Storage

$$EXMST = EXMRAT * WATBAL$$

Ground Water Recharge

$$GWRECH = PSUB * EXMST$$

Where:

PSUB could be estimated as follow

PSUB = 0.8 for Watershed with high soil permeability

PSUB = 0.3 for Watershed with low soil permeability

Change in Groundwater Storage

$$DELSTO = WATBAL - EXMST$$

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

DFLOW, BFLOW1, GWLOSS

Direct Flow

$$DFLOW = EXMST - GWRECH$$

Ground Water Layer Final Storage

$$GWSTORAGE2 = GWSTORAGE1 + GWRECH$$

River Base Flow from Ground Water Layer

$$BFLOW1 = GWF * GWSTORAGE2$$

Where:

GWF could be estimated as follow

GWF = 0.9 for Watershed with little sustained flow

GWF = 0.2 for Watershed with reliable sustained flow

Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of the Watershed

$$GWLOSS = GWSTORAGE2 * GWF$$

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

BFLOW2, FLOW

River Base Flow from Ground Water Layer outside of Watershed

BFLOW2 = (specified values adjusted for calibration)

Ground Water Layer Initial Storage for next Month Analysis

GWSTORAGE1 = GWSTORAGE2 - BFLOW1 - GWLOSS

Upper Soil Layer Moisture Storage Capacity at end of Time Period

STORAGE = STORAGE + DELSTO

River Discharge

*FLOW = $\frac{(RUNOFF + DFLOW + BFLOW1 + BFLOW2) * WATERSHED AREA}{(\#DAYS \text{ in } MONTH * 24 * 60 * 60)}$*

The river flow for each month is calculated following this procedure. It usually takes 20 iterations (years) for the monthly flows to converge.

HYDROLOGIC ANALYSIS

CALIBRATION

CALIBRATION IS ACHIEVED BY VARYING RFLK, PSUB, GWF, GWL

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Dams

Gravity Dam with Reservoir

Tyrolean Dam without Reservoir

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Turbines

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Turbines

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Turbines

FRANCIS TURBINE

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Turbines

KAPLAN TURBINE

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Type of Turbines

CROSSFLOW TURBINE

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Typical Turbine Efficiency

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Site Classification

SITE CLASSIFICATION		POWER RANGE
	Pico	$P \leq 50 \text{ KW}$
	Micro	$50 < P \leq 100 \text{ KW}$
	Mini	$100 < P \leq 500 \text{ KW}$
	Small	$500 < P \leq 1,000 \text{ KW}$
	Macro	$1,000 < P \leq 10,000 \text{ KW}$
	Large	$P > 10,000 \text{ KW}$

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Required Input

- River Monthly, Minimum, and Maximum Flow
- River Flow Exceedance Curve
- Turbine Design Flow
- Turbine Type
- Number of Turbines
- Dam Water Surface Elevation
- Reservoir Storage Area and Working Height
- Penstock Diameter, Length, and Friction Coefficient
- Canal Width, Length, and Friction Coefficient
- Power House Tailrace Elevation
- Generator Efficiency
- Powerline Efficiency

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Graphical Input

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Analysis Output

- Site Gross Power
- Monthly Average Power
- Yearly Minimum Power
- Yearly Maximum Power
- Site Total Energy Produced
- Site Average Efficiency
- Site Maximum Efficiency
- Penstock Head-loss Percentage
- Penstock Maximum Velocity
- Turbine Recommended Optimum Flow
- Turbine Suitability Graph
- Site Classification

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Flow Exceedance

Definition:

- The “Flow Exceedance” curve or the “Percent Exceeds” curve, represent the rating or the number of times in percent a given value of a river flow is equaled or exceeded.
- This graph is useful for setting the turbine flow and calculate the amount of energy that could be produced.

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Turbine Applicability

Turbine Type	Minimum Flow Range (m ³ /s)	Maximum Flow Range (m ³ /s)	Minimum Head (m)	Maximum Head (m)	Optimum Flow Exceedance (%)	Ratio Minimum Flow to Design Flow (%)
Cross-Flow	0.05	10.00	2.00	200.00	10	33
Francis	0.50	900.00	10.00	400.00	25	40
Pelton	0.01	60.00	50.00	1000.00	10	20
Turgo	0.01	10.00	50.00	500.00	20	20
Kaplan	0.50	50.00	4.00	100.00	15	35

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Design Flow

Set Range of River Flows

RiverFlowMin = *Minimum River Flow*

RiverFlowMax = *Maximum River Flow*

Set Project Design Flow

DesignFlow = *User input based on turbine type*

Set Penstock Flow

PipeFlow = *DesignFlow*

Set Maximum Controlling Flow

Case when $\text{PipeFlow} \leq \text{RiverFlowMax}$

$Q_{Max} = \text{PipeFlow}$

Case when $\text{PipeFlow} > \text{RiverFlowMax}$

$Q_{Max} = \text{RiverFlowMax}$

Set Turbine(s) Unit Flow

$\text{TurbineFlow} = \frac{Q_{Max} * 3}{(2 * N_{turbine} + 1)}$

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Penstock Losses

Entrance Loss

$$H_L = K_E \frac{V^2}{2G}$$

Bend Loss

$$H_L = K_B \frac{V^2}{2G}$$

Valve Loss

$$H_L = K_V \frac{V^2}{2G}$$

Pipe Loss

$$H_L = \frac{L * 19.613 n^2}{R^{4/3}} \frac{V^2}{2G}$$

Exit Loss

$$H_L = K_E \frac{V^2}{2G}$$

Penstock Efficiency

$$E_P = \frac{H - \sum H_L}{H}$$

Default Entrance Loss Coefficient

$$K_E = 0.04 \quad (\text{Bell Mouth})$$

Default Bend Loss Coefficient

$$K_B = 0.25 * \sqrt{\frac{\Phi}{90}}$$

$$\Phi = 15^\circ$$

#Bends = Penstock Length / 200 m
200 m bends spacing is defaulted

Default Valve Loss Coefficient

$$K_V = 0.17 \quad (\text{Gate Valve})$$

One valve is accounted for in VB Macro

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Turbines Efficiency

Cross-Flow Turbine Efficiency

$$E_T = -0.27946 + (13.068 * A) - (81.222 * A^2) + (275.787 * A^3) - (534.982 * A^4) + (592.367 * A^5) - (348.08 * A^6) + (84.1433 * A^7)$$

Francis Turbine Efficiency

$$E_T = -1.38959 + (17.6433 * A) - (70.5159 * A^2) + (174.261 * A^3) - (273.511 * A^4) + (266.656 * A^5) - (146.992 * A^6) + (34.6991 * A^7)$$

Pelton Turbine Efficiency

$$E_T = 0.00714 + (11.0712 * A) - (63.874 * A^2) + (207.119 * A^3) - (396.07 * A^4) + (440.759 * A^5) - (262.98 * A^6) + (64.8347 * A^7)$$

Turgo Turbine Efficiency

$$E_T = 0.131789 + (6.86047 * A) - (35.21 * A^2) + (105.665 * A^3) - (186.658 * A^4) + (191.065 * A^5) - (104.956 * A^6) + (23.9621 * A^7)$$

Kaplan Turbine Efficiency

$$E_T = -0.157845 + (5.16567 * A) - (12.5331 * A^2) + (18.6549 * A^3) - (16.1621 * A^4) + (6.06582 * A^5) + (0.91835 * A^6) - (1.05123 * A^7)$$

Where A is the ratio of the River Flow over the Turbine Rated Flow

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Water to Wire

Power Plant Efficiency

$$E = E_P * E_T * E_G * E_L$$

Where:

E_P is the pipe efficiency

E_T is the turbine efficiency

E_G is the generator efficiency

E_L is the transmission line efficiency

Power

$$P = \rho g E Q H$$

Typical Water to Wire efficiency varies from around 65% to 75%. Higher Water to Wire efficiency is possible by using large pipes that will decrease the head-loss. However, the increase in pipe size is not always economical.

HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS

Sample Output

OPTIMUM OPERATING CONDITION FOR DIFFERENT TURBINE TYPE								
FLOW (m ³ /s)	PGRS (KW)	PMAX (KW)	PAVG (KW)	PMIN (KW)	TOTAL ENERGY (KWH)	E MAX %	E AVG %	TURBINE TYPE
4.2000	2677.04	1755.49	1273.71	634.26	11,157,736.77	65.58%	47.58%	Francis

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL GENERAL SITES MAP

EXHIBIT D-1

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 1 OF 7

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 2 OF 7

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 3 OF 7

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 4 OF 7

EXHIBIT D-5

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 5 OF 7

EXHIBITS

EXHIBITS

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 7 OF 7

EXHIBIT D-8

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME

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